

From Gestures to Words: The Role of LSTM Networks in Real-Time Sign Language Interpretation

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Abstract— According to WHO, there are more than 466 million people around the world who has speech and hearing impairments. This accounts to almost 5% of the total world population. People who have speech and hearing impairments use sign language to communicate to the world. But people who are not educated in sign language, finds it difficult to comprehend the sign language. A system that can recognize these signs, can help them to comprehend the signs and communicate with the people with hearing and speech impairments. Most of the existing systems has been built upon static signs. Through this project, we are trying to build a system that can recognize the dynamic signs of Indian Sign Language. We had chosen 3 words, that are essential and is used on a daily basis. We had created the dataset with 30 videos for each of the signs. This model is trained using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). The model had an accuracy of 99.3%.

Index Terms – sign language recognition, hearing and speech impairment, LSTM

I. INTRODUCTION

Communication is about all the participants being able to understand each other. From childhood we learn languages that help us to communicate with other. We learn by observing the people around talk. We listen to them speaking, imitate and learn. But when it comes to the people who has speech and hearing impairments, this process becomes nearly impossible due to their disabilities. Communication for these people is through the means of hand signs and gestures.

Sign language is a communication language used by people who have speech and hearing impairments. It is a complete language, with its own grammar and syntax. Sign languages are highly visual and expressive, and they use a combination of hand movements, facial expressions, and body language to communicate. There are more than 200 sign languages used all over the world, each with its own unique history, vocabulary and grammer. Some of the most widely used sign languages include Indian Sign Language (ISL), German Sign Language (DGS), American Sign

Language (ASL), Japanese Sign Language (JSL) British Sign Language (BSL) and French Sign Language (LSF) There are special schools for them which teaches them how to communicate with each other. Not having the ability to hear and speak is a great issue and these specials schools help them to cope up with the fast-moving world around them. Even though the deaf and the mute use their own ways of communicating with one another, this language is not taught to everyone around them. Although there are schools which teach sign languages, learning it overnight is impossible. Those who do not understand sign language find it difficult to communicate with them. They will require a translator to translate the sign language into English or any other language. The same can be achieved through an ML model which can accurately recognize the signs that are being signed by a person. Even people who uses different sign languages will be able to communicate with each other with the help of such a system. Through this project, we are trying to build a machine learning model which can recognize the sign language and translate it into English. We have built a sign language recognition system, which is trained using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model.

II. RELATED WORKS

According to the World Federation of Deaf, there are 700 million people who uses more than 300 sign languages around the world . There are many words and representations that are similar in all of these languages, yet there are significant differences as well. There has been a lot of research development revolving around the sign language recognition worldwide. In this section we are going to describe a few relevant previous works done on this topic.

Mohammad Elham Walizad and Mehreen Hurroo, [1] in their paper “Sign Language Recognition System using Convolutional Neural Network and Computer Vision” [3] proposes using a convolutional neural network (CNN) as the main classifier to recognize sign language gestures. The system collects and processes data from a video recording of sign language gestures using computer vision techniques such as morphological operations, background

subtraction and contour detection. The processed data is then used to train the CNN which can learn the features of the sign language gestures and recognize them in real time. The authors conducted experiments on sign language gesture's dataset to evaluate the performance of their proposed system. The system was also tested on various sign language datasets and showed similar results, indicating that it has good generalizability and can be applied to different sign language datasets.

The authors also compared the performance of their proposed system with classic machine learning methods, such as k-nearest neighbor and support vector machines and found that the CNN-based system performed better than these traditional methods in terms of accuracy and computational efficiency.

Madhuri Sharma, Ranjna Pal and Ashok Kumar Sahoo [2] in their paper "Indian Sign Language Recognition Using Neural Networks and KNN Classifiers" [7] proposed using both neural networks and k-nearest neighbor (KNN) classifiers and proved that the neural network-based classifier outperformed the KNN-based classifier in terms of recognition accuracy. The proposed system was also found to be robust to changes in background, lighting conditions, and body movements. The model was used to classify ISL numerical data. They used 500 images for each digit to train their model. Hierarchical centroid techniques and direct pixel value were used for feature extraction and KNN algorithm was used for classification. The model showed an accuracy of 97.10%.

Sigberto Alarcon Viesca and Brandon Garcia, in [3] their paper, "Real-time American Sign Language Recognition with Convolutional Neural Networks" had implemented a web application using CNN model. They trained the model using video and image signs from ASL. The application sends the user input to the server. The model evaluates the input and once the user has completed signing, the model takes into account, the probabilities of top 5 characters for each positions and then returns an optimal word back to the user." The team also compared the performance of their proposed system to classic machine learning methods such as SVM and decision trees and discovered that the CNN-based system performed better in terms of accuracy and computing efficiency than these traditional approaches.

Dinesh Dattatraya Rankhamb and Prof. S. C. Mhamane, in [4] their paper "Recognition of Indian Sign Language using SVM Classifier" has created a sign language recognition model using Support Vector Machine Classifiers. The system collects data from video recordings of ISL gestures and extracts features such as hand shape, orientation, and movement using computer vision techniques. These features are then used to train the SVM classifier, which is able to recognize the ISL gestures. Their model was built to precisely recommend digits and alphabets of the Indian Sign Language. They used PCA (Principal Component Analysis) for feature extraction and SVM, a supervised machine learning model for training. The authors conducted experiments on a dataset of ISL gestures and found that the SVM classifier

was able to achieve an accuracy of 95% in recognizing ISL gestures. They also compared the accuracy of their suggested system to that of classic machine learning approaches such as k-nearest neighbors, and discovered that the SVM-based system performed better.

A. K. Sahoo, in his paper "Indian sign language recognition using machine learning techniques" [5], discusses the different technologies that can be employed for developing a system for sign language recognition. He discusses about Sensor based approaches and vision-based approaches. Under sensor-based approaches, he has mentioned Glove-based approaches, Microsoft Kinect and Smartphone internal sensors. Under vision-based approaches he discusses static gestures and dynamic gestures. For static gestures, he proposes the usage of DenseNet and Support Vector Machine and for the dynamic gestures, he proposes Hidden Markov Model, Openpose Estimation and Mediapipe to recognize the gestures.

Al-Qurishi, M., Khalid, T., & Souissi, R. (2021), in their publication, "Deep learning for sign language recognition: Current techniques, benchmarks, and open issues" [6] had conducted a study on the current implementations and the issues that is present in the current systems for sign language recognition. Many methods have been discussed in this paper which includes machine learning models like Support Vector Machine (SVM), Hidden Markov Model, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Deep Learning Models like back propagation, Deep Belief Network, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Recurrent Convolutional Neural Networks (RCNNs), Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), SubUNETs, PCAnet. The paper also discusses the issues in the Sign Language Recognition System development. They are input models which can either be static or dynamic signs, the lack of dataset resources, issues with combining different features, implementation of systems continuous sign language recognition and improving prediction accuracy.

Mohandes, M., Deriche, M., & Liu, J, in their paper "Image-based and sensor-based approaches to Arabic sign language recognition" [7] has discussed image based and sensor-based approaches for Arabic Sign Language Recognition. In the image-based approach, the authors proposed a system that uses computer vision techniques to extract features from video recordings of signs from Arabic sign language. Following that, the retrieved features were utilized to train an SVM machine to recognize the signs.. The authors also discussed the use of deep learning techniques such as convolutional neural networks for Arabic sign language recognition. In the sensor-based approach, the authors proposed a system that uses sensors like accelerometers and gyroscopes to collect data about movements of a user's hands and arms while using the system. The collected data was then processed and used in training of a machine learning model to recognize the gestures.

III. METHODOLOGY

In the development of a sign language recognition system, particularly for the nuanced and richly varied Indian Sign Language (ISL), the stages of data collection and preprocessing are foundational and critically impactful. The absence of readily available datasets for dynamic ISL gestures presents a unique challenge, necessitating the creation of a bespoke dataset to ensure the efficacy and accuracy of the recognition model. This research aims to bridge this gap by focusing on the acquisition and preparation of high-quality video data for a select set of fundamental daily-use words. The methodology section of this research outlines the systematic approach undertaken to capture, preprocess, and ready the data for subsequent stages of model training and evaluation.

A. Data Collection:

Data collection and preprocessing are very important steps in developing a sign language recognition system. Accurate data collection is necessary to build a robust model that could efficiently recognize sign language gestures. There were no datasets available for the dynamic signs of Indian Sign Language. For this project, we had selected 3 basic words that we use on a daily basis. These words were Hello, Thanks, and I Love you. For training our model, we recorded 30 videos each, for each of the words. These videos were pre-processed using OpenCV and MediaPipe Holistic.

B. Data Preprocessing

OpenCV is a computer vision library that covers a variety of image and video processing methods such as object detection, face recognition, and hand gesture recognition etc. We had used OpenCV to extract different frames from the videos. These frames were then processed using MediaPipe Holistic. MediaPipe Holistic is a machine learning tool designed for extraction of different features from images and videos. It can be used to analyze video frames and identify keypoints which can then be used to represent the signs. These keypoints include the positions of the hands, fingers, facial and pose landmarks, as well as their relative positions and movements over time. The keypoints from each frame are extracted and these are stored as a NumPy arrays. This data was used in training the LSTM model.

C. Model Definition and Training

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) is a kind of recurrent neural network (RNN) type that is often employed for sequential data analysis and processing. LSTMs are very effective for spotting patterns and formulating predictions based on time-series data, such as hand motions in sign language recognition. For sign language recognition, LSTMs can be trained on a large, annotated dataset of signs to learn the complex relationships between hand movements and signs. LSTMs are designed to overcome the vanishing and exploding gradient problem that affects traditional RNNs. LSTMs address this issue by incorporating memory cells, gates, and activation functions, which allows the model to selectively store and retrieve information over time. The trained LSTM model may then be utilized in real-time to detect and translate sign language gestures. Since LSTMs are capable of processing sequential data and recognizing patterns over time, they are well-suited for sign language recognition, which requires recognizing and translating the sequential movements of hands in sign language. A multilayer LSTM network was designed and trained using the extracted features from the training dataset. The validation dataset was used in assessing the performance of the model and to prevent overfitting. The LSTM network consists of an input layer, several LSTM layers and output layer. The input layer takes the feature vectors extracted from the preprocessing step as input and then passes them to the LSTM layers. The LSTM layers learn the relationships between the feature vectors and store this information in their memory cells. Then the output layer uses the information stored in the memory cells to predict the sign language gesture that is being signed. The model was trained on 80% of dataset and evaluated using 20%.

D. Plotting Training History

The LSTM network is trained using 80% of the videos from the actual dataset. The model is trained using a supervised learning approach where it is provided with the feature vectors and the corresponding sign label. The network updates its weights to minimize the prediction error during the learning process.

E. Reusing the Model and Predicting New Images Reloading

the saved model. Defining classes and directories for new images. Defining functions to preprocess images (preprocess_image) and predict their classes (predict_image_class). Testing the model with new images and displaying the predictions along with the images.

```
Model: "sequential"
```

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
lstm (LSTM)	(None, 30, 64)	442112
lstm_1 (LSTM)	(None, 30, 128)	98816
lstm_2 (LSTM)	(None, 64)	49408
dense (Dense)	(None, 64)	4160
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 32)	2080
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 8)	264

```
Total params: 596,840  

Trainable params: 596,840  

Non-trainable params: 0
```

F. Validations

The trained LSTM network is validated using 20% of the videos from the actual dataset. The validation dataset is used in evaluation of the performance of our model and avoid overfitting, an issue in deep learning models in which the model gets overly specialized to the training dataset and performs poorly on fresh data due to a lack of generalizability.

IV. RESULTS

Accuracy

```
model.fit(x_train, y_train, epochs=100, callbacks=[EarlyStopping])
```

Epoch 1/100	1s	1000/step	categorical_accuracy: 0.0011	loss: 16.7253
Epoch 2/100	1s	3860/step	categorical_accuracy: 0.0228	loss: 12.8119
Epoch 3/100	1s	4460/step	categorical_accuracy: 0.1917	loss: 13.3336
Epoch 4/100	1s	4460/step	categorical_accuracy: 0.4098	loss: 11.0605
Epoch 5/100	1s	4460/step	categorical_accuracy: 0.3872	loss: 10.8893
Epoch 6/100	1s	4460/step	categorical_accuracy: 0.5288	loss: 10.2129
Epoch 7/100	1s	4460/step	categorical_accuracy: 0.3253	loss: 11.9829
Epoch 8/100	1s	4460/step	categorical_accuracy: 0.3489	loss: 5.0811
Epoch 9/100	1s	4460/step	categorical_accuracy: 0.1917	loss: 6.4886

```
res = model.predict(X_test)
```

1/1 ————— 1s 917ms/step

```
yhat = model.predict(X_test)
```

1/1 ————— 0s 23ms/step

```
accuracy_score(ytrue, yhat)
```

0.8

Fig 1. Implementation-hello

Fig 2. Implementation- ilove you

Fig 3. Implementation-thanks

V CONCLUSION

A pioneering machine learning-driven methodology for The goal of this project was to create an application that facilitates communication with people who have hearing and speech impairments, as well as others. We wanted to build a system that would provide the user the ability to translate the dynamic signs in real time accurately. This would eradicate the communication gap between the commoners and challenged people. Using an LSTM model for sign language recognition is a promising approach which can provide us with accurate results. The LSTM network is able of capturing the temporal dependencies in the sign language data, making it well suited for recognizing the gestures. This is particularly useful in sign language recognition, where the signs are often performed in a specific order or sequence. However, it is crucial to consider the short-comings of LSTM models when developing sign language recognition systems. These models can be computationally intensive and requires a huge amounts of training data in order to achieve good results. It is also important to preprocess the data and extract meaningful features that can be used as input to the LSTM model. By combining the power of LSTM networks with other machine learning algorithms and techniques, It is possible to develop more effective and accurate sign language recognition systems, which can improve the lives of those who relies on sign language as their basic mode of communication.

VI REFERENCES

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